

THE MAIN CONTENT OF THE NATIONAL IDEA AT THE NEW STAGE OF UZBEKISTAN'S DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: Adoption of the concept of development of the national idea at a new stage of Uzbekistan's development is due to the fact that our country is becoming more deeply integrated into the world community, the aspiration of our people to take a place among the developed nations of the world, material-economic factors, high technologies, as well as the development of spiritual factors.

Key words: national idea, ideology, patriotism, justice, people's consent. enlightenment against ignorance.

It is worth noting that in the world, new technologies are increasingly entering the field of ideology, and attempts to use it for healthy and unhealthy purposes continue. In Uzbekistan, a strong national idea and a national program for technological development and modernization of the domestic market [1] are being put on the agenda. It urges the society to work on the basis of new technologies to increase the efficiency of all spheres in the implementation of spiritual and educational reforms, the need for the idea of national progress and the stage of development of the state and society.

Various forms and means of communication with the people at all levels of public life, including public receptions, virtual receptions, reception of the Prime Minister, reports of responsible and official leaders in local councils of people's deputies, mobile receptions, social problems, living conditions of people directly going to the places. The widespread use of methods such as learning serves to improve the principles of the national idea by strengthening the foundations of national statehood, ultimately ensuring the interests and well-being of the population.

Every society needs a national idea. Today's Uzbekistan, which is striving for national growth, is developing its development in innovative development, in forming an active citizenship position in citizens, in being proactive, in forming an independent worldview and positive thinking skills, in being responsible and demanding from everyone in one's labor activities, in relations in society. we can see it in tending to ensure the priority of justice, in being uncompromising and firm in fighting corruption, in fighting ignorance with enlightenment. It is worth noting that today our people, their social consciousness, their attitude to life are gradually changing, the political maturity of our compatriots, the sense of civic responsibility and involvement in the events happening in our country and in the world is increasing. All this is manifested in the fact that the main idea of the great goal of national recovery and national progress, which ensures the consistent development of our country and the achievement of new milestones, has emerged.

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the need for the idea of national growth arises from the main idea of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The implementation of

the basic concepts defined in it will serve to deeply instill them into the hearts and minds of our people. Including

1. The feeling of a single Motherland.
2. Justice is the rule of law.
3. People's consent.
4. Enlightenment against ignorance.
5. Concepts such as innovative development define a new image and main task of our main idea at the new stage of Uzbekistan's development.

If we pay attention to the idea of national growth, we will see that it includes national and universal values. Because the sense of the single Motherland, the principles of justice and the rule of law and the people's consent, from the history of our national statehood formed over the centuries, represent the way of life and worldview of our ancestors. In the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the concepts of struggle against ignorance with enlightenment and innovative development are based on universal values of our modern development. In today's world, it is impossible to imagine the development of any field without innovative ideas and scientific achievements. The greatest wealth of mankind is the enormous intellectual and spiritual potential of this nation.

We express the need for the idea of national growth with the following suggestions and recommendations.

First of all, we believe that in order to meet the need for the national idea, raising spiritual and educational foundations should be taught as a subject at all stages of education. Because instilling the national idea with enlightenment gives an effective result.

Secondly, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan stated at the high podium of the UN, - "The youth of the world today are the largest generation in the history of mankind in terms of numbers, because they make up 2 billion people. The well-being of our planet tomorrow depends on how our children grow up to be human beings [2] - Uzbekistan stated its position. Therefore, by inculcating the concepts and principles of the national idea into the minds and hearts of young people, the expected strategic goal will be achieved.

Thirdly, it is necessary to use modern innovative technologies to introduce the idea of national development to the general public. In particular, a new image of Uzbekistan will be created by improving people's well-being, bringing public relations with state agencies to a new level. In this, the mass media takes the lead and encourages all our citizens to be active.

Also, special attention is being paid to reducing state participation in the economy, fully transitioning to market relations, opening a wider path to the freedom of private property and private entrepreneurship, and active use of public-private partnership relations in all areas. All conditions and opportunities are being created for the full use of underground and surface resources, human resources.

At the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, new qualitative changes in the hearts and minds of citizens are taking place in harmony with the increase in the standard of living. The fact that reliable protection of the rights and interests of the citizens of Uzbekistan, no matter where they are in the world, by the state is becoming a reality, all the necessary mechanisms are being used in this regard, the feeling of pride of the members of the society for their

people and the Motherland, the state's guarantee of justice and legal rights. is increasing his confidence in his potential. Vigorous reforms taking place on the basis of the action strategy call for strengthening the people's confidence in the future, mobilizing it for creative work, and actively fighting against the evils in society, in particular, indifference, neglect, and corruption.

References:

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